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Abstract. The object of study in the course of medical Latin are words and phrases that denote special concepts of medical science. Such words and phrases are called terms, and their combination forms medical terminology - the professional language of medical workers. A medical specialist must competently use the constantly updated professional language and understand the laws that determine the emergence of terms.

Doctors of any country use many international, generally accepted terms that arose based on ancient Greek and Latin. These terms are universal and understandable to professionals regardless of their nationality. Such international terms constitute the main fund of medical science. The most ancient period includes such terms as epidemic (epidemia), bronchus (bronchus), herpes (herpes), carcinoma (carcinoma), and emphysema (emphysema)

The terminologies of individual sciences consist of tens and hundreds of thousands of terms. The starting point in terminology is the position that the purpose of a term is to briefly, accurately and unambiguously express a scientific concept. To do this, the term must have the following criteria: adequacy, unambiguity.

In actual terminology, not all terms meet these requirements. Therefore, specialists from various sciences, including medicine, pay great attention to streamlining and standardizing their professional language.

Key words: terminological system, root term elements, Greek prefixes, final element, anatomical-histological terminology, pharmaceutical terminology and clinical terminology, subsystems.

INTRODUCTION

The terminological system of modern medicine consists of many subsystems, among which three leading ones stand out: anatomical-histological terminology, pharmaceutical terminology and clinical terminology.

The names of functional disorders are usually composed using a combination of prefix and root term elements. Of the prefix TEs, the prefix dys- is most often used in combination with the final root TE: dyskinesia, ae f - dyskinesia, a disorder of coordinated motor acts. A combination of the noun dysfunctio, onis f - dysfunction and the name of a specific organ is also used: dysfunctio renum - kidney dysfunction. Complete cessation or absence of some function or physiological process is expressed using the prefix a - (an - before the vowel): aphagia, ae f - aphagia, complete inability to swallow; anuria, ae f - anuria, failure of urine to enter the bladder

The names of pathological processes and conditions are composed using prefix, suffix and root TEs, and are expressed by Latin noun terms. At the same time, a definition is often added to noun terms that characterize the peculiarity of a given pathological process (acute, chronic, complete, partial, etc.).

Almost all prefixes are used as prefix TEs, but Greek prefixes are much more common than Latin ones. Their meaning in clinical terms usually coincides with their meaning in anatomical terms.

However, it is often difficult to determine the meaning of the Greek prefix in many terms, since, firstly, the root morphemes of such terms without prefixes are not used in medical terminology, and secondly, the Greek prefixes themselves have many meanings. Therefore, in such cases, it is necessary to assimilate the term without isolating the prefix in it and without conducting a morphological analysis of the word, for example: diabetes, *ae m* - diabetes, the name of a group of diseases of an endocrine nature, characterized by excessive excretion of urine from the body.

The terms “pharmaceutics” and “pharmacy” are of ancient Greek origin and go back to the word *pharmakon* medicine. Subsequently, through Latin, these two terms entered all the languages of Europe. Medicine traditionally uses Latin and Latinized Greek words in the names of raw materials for drug production, in drug names and in formulations.

The list of Latin names of dosage forms and preparations is the International Pharmaceutical Nomenclature. From time to time, as some drugs or dosage forms become obsolete and other drugs or dosage forms become available, the list of pharmaceutical terms is reviewed and updated.

Results and discussion

Uppercase and lowercase letters in dictionary form and as part of a pharmaceutical term are very important. It is written with a capital letter both in dictionary form and as part of a term:

1. Names of medicinal plants: *Chamomilla*, *ae f* - chamomile; *Flores Chamomillae* – chamomile flowers; *Frangula*, *ae f* – buckthorn; *Decoctum corticis Frangulae* – decoction of buckthorn bark.

2. Names of chemical elements and cations: *Ferrum*, *i n* – iron; *Sirupus Aloes cum Ferro* – aloe syrup with iron; *Strychninum*, *i n* – strychnine; *Solutio Strychnini nitratis* – solution of strychnine nitrate.

3. Names of medicines: *Prednisolonum*, *i n* – prednisolone; *Tabulettae Prednisoloni* – prednisolone tablets; *Leonurus*, *i m* – motherwort; *Tinctura Leonuri* – motherwort tincture.

4. Words equivalent to medicines: *Amylum*, *i n* – starch; *Gelatina*, *ae f* – gelatin(a); *Gelatosa*, *ae f* – gelatose; *Propolisum*, *i n* – propolis; *Saccharum*, *i n* – sugar.

Clinical terminology (from the Greek *klinike* (techne) - care for bedridden patients) is the most extensive section of medical terminology. The names of various diseases and abnormalities, research and treatment methods, clinical specialties and specialists are presented here. All these names are basically nouns. Such nouns can be single-root words (*asthma*, *atis n* - asthma; *hernia*, *ae f* - hernia). However, in most cases they are complex in composition and consist mainly of Greek word-forming elements, or term elements (TE): *hyperaesthesia* - increased sensitivity.

There are affix and root TEs. Affixal TEs are prefixes and suffixes. For example, the prefix *hypo* – forms terms with the meaning “below normal”: *hypothermia* – hypothermia, decreased temperature, *hypothermia*; *hypothyreosis* – hypothyroidism, decreased thyroid function; *hypoxia* – hypoxia, decreased oxygen levels in tissues. The suffix – *oma* usually means “tumor”: *lipoma*, a tumor of adipose tissue; *odontoma* – odontoma, a tumor of dental tissue. Root TEs are the roots or bases of Greek and sometimes Latin nouns, adjectives or pronouns. It is customary to divide root TEs into initial and final ones. Initial TEs are combined with suffixes or final TEs. For example, TE *angi* – with the meaning “vessel” can be combined with the suffixes – *itis* or – *oma* in the terms

angioma (angioma, tumor from vascular tissue) and angiitis (angiitis, inflammation of the walls of blood vessels). At the same time, this TE can also be combined with root terminal TE: angiosclerosis (angiosclerosis, hardening of the walls of blood vessels), angiospasmus (angiospasm, spasm of blood vessels). The initial TE is usually joined to another, including the final TE, with the help of a connecting vowel - o -: bronchospasmus - bronchospasm, narrowing of the bronchi. If the TE to which the initial TE is attached begins with a vowel, then the connecting - o - is usually skipped: nephrectomia - nephrectomy, kidney removal operation. However, sometimes this rule is not observed and the connecting - o - is retained: acroaesthesia - increased sensitivity distal parts of the body.

Root TEs can often act as both initial and final term elements, for example: nos- and -nosis (disease, disease), cf.: nosologia, ae f - nosology, the study of the forms of diseases and their classification; zoonosis, is f - zoonosis, infectious diseases transmitted from animals to humans. In such cases, students are required to know both of these options and give them in an oral or written answer: disease, disease - nos-, - nosis.

Root TEs can connect with each other, forming multicomponent structures: chole (bile) + cyst (bladder) -> cholecyst - (gallbladder): cholecystographia - cholecystography - radiography of the gallbladder.

Root TEs can sometimes have multiple meanings. Thus, the initial TE kerat can have 2 meanings: 1) cornea of the eye; 2) the stratum corneum of the epidermis of the skin, cf.: keratitis - keratitis, inflammation of the cornea of the eye; kerotosis - keratosis, the general name for skin diseases characterized by thickening of the stratum corneum of the epidermis.

The names of sciences, specialties and branches of medicine are most often formed using the final TE - logia: ophthalmologia, ae f - ophthalmology. Based on TE - logia, adjectives are formed with the final element -logicus, a, um (Russian equivalent - logical), which indicates belonging to some group of sciences, branches of clinical medicine, methods of research or treatment: bacteriologicus, a, um - bacteriological related to bacteriology.

Some names of sections of clinical medicine are formed using the final TE - iatria: geriatria, ae f - geriatrics, a section of clinical medicine devoted to diseases of old age and methods of their treatment.

The names of some sections of clinical medicine are compiled descriptively: morbi interni - internal diseases; morbi infectiosi - infectious diseases.

The names of some clinicians are formed using TE - pathologus and - iater, and such terms always correlate with the names of the corresponding sections of clinical medicine: neuropathologia, ae f - neuropathologus, i m - neurologist, a specialist in diseases of the peripheral nervous system. Latin names of specialists, which in Russian equivalents have a final element - ist, are masculine nouns of the first declension with a final element - ista: infectious disease specialist - infectionista, ae m - a specialist in infectious diseases.

CONCLUSION

The names of specialists that have the final element - path in Russian equivalents - are II declension nouns with the final element - pathus: naturopath - naturopathus, i m - a doctor who uses only natural remedies (living and non-living nature) for treatment.

Today, Latin is not only a memory of the philosophers, orators, and poets of Ancient Rome, but also an indispensable attribute of the modern world. Latin is firmly entrenched in scientific terminology in many fields of knowledge, especially medicine, biology and law. Therefore,

medical, biological and legal Latin are even distinguished separately. In medicine, almost all medical terms are of Latin-Greek origin.

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